

HEART: THE DEVELOPED LESSON EXEMPLARS IN UNDERSTANDING CULTURE, SOCIETY, AND POLITICS FOR INNOVATION AND CULTURALLY RESPONSIVE EDUCATION

Emelita B. Ferrer

Social Studies Department, Laguna College of Business and Arts, Calamba City, Laguna Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15706301>

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study was to develop and validate lesson exemplars in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Innovation and Culturally Responsive Education, which fosters empathy, respect, and inclusive education. A descriptive developmental research design was adopted, and pretests and posttests were administered to 44 students at Calamba City Science Integrated School (CCSIS). Purposive random sampling was employed, selecting one specific section of Grade 11 from the academic track, mainly, STEM strand. A Researcher-made lesson exemplars, pretest/posttest, were validated by the experts and was used to gather data. This had a Lawshe Content Validity Index of 1.00 and Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient of 0.872 for the pretest and posttest, and 0.921 for the instrument. Four-point Likert Scale, Mean, and Paired T-test were used to analyze the data. Results demonstrated remarkable improvement, with 61.36% of students achieving "Outstanding" performance, 31.82% very satisfactory, and 6.82% satisfactory. No students remained in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category. The substantial improvement in posttest scores revealed the success of the exemplars in enhancing student understanding and engagement, with an overall performance of 89.84 %. There was a significant difference between the mean scores of the students on the pretest and posttest. The probability value is .000, which is less than the level of significance of $P < .05$. The study's implications underscore the transformative potential of using validated lesson exemplars to promote higher engagement, better understanding, and improved performance.

Keywords: *Development and Validation, Lesson Exemplars, Innovation, Culturally Responsive Education, Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics*

INTRODUCTION

Education in the 21st century demands innovative and culturally responsive teaching approaches that enhance student engagement, critical thinking, and inclusivity. In teaching the Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP) subject, it is crucial to offer learning experiences that embrace diverse perspectives, foster social awareness, and equip students with the competencies needed to navigate an increasingly complex global landscape.

Improving the educational experiences and outcomes of students from varied cultural origins presents a variety of problems for educators, especially those who feel underrepresented, discriminated, disadvantaged, and marginalized. There are issues and barriers to equity and inclusion in education that need to be addressed. Students in the classroom should feel represented and included regardless of their cultural backgrounds in lessons and school activities to reach their full potential.

Aligned with Vice President Sara Duterte's MATATAG agenda, which emphasized learner care, inclusive education, and positive learning environments, the Department of Education (DepEd) highlighted the vital role of teachers in crafting educational settings that value diversity (PPST Domain 3). This domain underlined educators' need to recognize, understand, and respect students' varied characteristics, perspectives, and experiences, using these as foundational elements in lesson planning and instructional design.

DepEd took an inclusive and diverse approach to its policies and programs, ensuring its accessibility to all students and staff, regardless of their background, culture, or abilities. This included providing accommodation and support for students and staff with disabilities, as well as programs and initiatives that promoted cultural diversity and inclusiveness.

Inclusive education had been the core of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, which had been designed to promote equity and address disparities among students and staff. As prescribed under Republic Act No. 10533, DepEd had adhered to different principles, ensuring that the curriculum was learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally relevant, responsive, and research-based, as well as implementing initiatives that aimed to eliminate discrimination and address issues of equity and inclusion in education.

This study proposed the development of innovative lesson exemplars that leveraged the latest educational research and pedagogical practices. As educators strove to meet the diverse needs of their students, the importance of understanding culture, society, and politics (UCSP) had never been more crucial. These exemplars were designed to promote active learning, critical thinking, and empathy among students,

ensuring that they not only grasped the content but also developed a deep appreciation for cultural diversity and social dynamics, meeting the needs of learners aligned with the curriculum.

This study aimed to enhance UCSP instruction by equipping teachers with effective tools and strategies to foster creativity and cultural responsiveness in their teaching. Through the development and validation of lesson exemplars, the research sought to empower educators to create inclusive and dynamic learning environments that encourage students to be actively engaged, informed, and socially responsible individuals.

Teaching methods needed to be innovative to engage students and prepare them for a world that had been changing rapidly. The application of culturally responsive education (CRE) that valued students' cultural origins, experiences, and viewpoints as vital assets in the learning process was a crucial component of this innovation. The goal of culturally responsive education was to establish inclusive and stimulating learning environments while acknowledging the varied origins and experiences of students.

The careful creation and validation of lesson exemplars in UCSP were the focus of this study, which aimed to promote creativity and build an educational atmosphere sensitive to cultural differences. This research was motivated by the realization that well-crafted, culturally appropriate instructional exemplars could significantly alter the social studies curriculum. Teachers could successfully bridge the gap between abstract ideas and practical applications, promoting greater engagement and comprehension, by creating instructional exemplars that addressed the diverse cultural backgrounds and life experiences of the students.

Additionally, the goal of this study was to encourage students to think critically and to be globally competent. With the purpose of providing students with the analytical tools needed to navigate a more interconnected and multicultural world, the prepared lesson exemplars exposed students to a wide range of perspectives and challenged them to understand complex socio-political issues.

In essence, developing and validating lesson exemplars in UCSP for innovation and culturally responsive education was a critical step in creating a more inclusive, equitable, and successful educational environment. Through this research, the researcher hoped not only to improve the quality of UCSP instruction but to raise a new generation of informed, empathetic, and culturally competent global citizens. By integrating innovative strategies, students explored the dynamic interconnections between culture, society, and politics.

Finally, this study aimed to inform and inspire educators and researchers in their efforts to improve the quality and relevance of social studies education by providing insights into effective ways of developing culturally responsive instructional materials—active, student-centered teaching techniques that promoted involvement and teamwork, characterized innovative classrooms. Incorporating students' experiences, perspectives,

and backgrounds into the classroom was highly valued in culturally responsive education. This approach recognized diversity and promoted inclusivity to foster a learning environment where all students felt valued, respected, and supported.

Research Objectives

The main purpose of this study was to develop and validate lesson exemplars in teaching Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Innovation and Culturally Responsive Education. This study aims to shed light on the following:

1. Design and develop lesson exemplars for teaching Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP) to Grade 11 STEM students.
2. Establish the content validity and reliability of the developed lesson exemplars.
3. Determine whether a significant difference exists between the pretest and posttest scores of Grade-11 STEM students who used the lesson exemplars.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a design and development research methodology to establish a robust empirical foundation for creating instructional materials, specifically Lesson Exemplars. The ADDIE model, consisting of five key phases—Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation—was applied to develop lesson exemplars for Senior High School (SHS) students in the subject of Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). A descriptive developmental research design was adopted, and pretest and posttests were administered to Grade 11 students at Calamba City Science Integrated School (CCSIS). Descriptive analysis was conducted to examine how lesson exemplars supported teachers in implementing culturally responsive education. The study employed purposive random sampling and selected one section of Grade 11 STEM students, totaling 44 participants.

The respondents of this study were educators and experts with extensive backgrounds in social studies. These interraters were selected for their knowledge and expertise in the subject of Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). Among the respondents were experienced senior high school teachers and academic experts who regularly deliver UCSP lessons, ensuring their insights were from Program Specialist, Principal, and Assistant Principal. The respondents' combined professional expertise and practical experience significantly contributed to the depth and validity of the study's findings. Their constructive critiques, thoughtful recommendations, and honest feedback greatly contributed to the refinement and improvement of this study. The lesson exemplars were validated by five (5) experts, three (3) from LCBA, two (2) from the division of Calamba, and fifteen (15) interraters in Araling Panlipunan from the division of Calamba, and one from a private university. It is comprised of (1) one Education Program Specialist, one (1) Principal, one (1) Assistant Principal, one (1) Assistant Professor of private University, five (5) Master Teachers, three (3) Head Teachers, one (1) seasoned Teacher III from the public school. The effectiveness of the lesson exemplars was evaluated through the administration of pretests and posttests to the same group of Grade

11 STEM students. Their performance was analyzed to measure the impact of the instructional materials. Using the ADDIE model as a framework, the lesson exemplars were iteratively developed and validated to align with curriculum standards and culturally responsive education principles.

The study used different research instruments during its implementation. These were the development of Senior High School (SHS) Innovative and Culturally Responsive Lessons Exemplars and an assessment tool based on the prescribed learning curriculum of Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). Specifically, the researcher used an expert's evaluation checklist of the lesson exemplar, which was an adapted instrument from the division of Calamba. Additionally, the researcher-made pretest and posttest assessment questionnaires validated in the division of Calamba by the EPS and one Master Teacher from Calamba City Science Integrated School and other experts from the Laguna College of Business Art to assess its usefulness before, and after the administration of the material. The researcher also employed the institutionalized 4-point Likert Scale and in addition, the researcher interpreted the result of the pretest and posttest using the Levels of Proficiency adopting DepEd Order 73, S. 2012.

The researcher-made lesson exemplars guided by the specific problem presented in Chapter 1. The lessons were validated and rated by 15 experts, who had expertise in the field of Social Studies. The experts were requested to validate the lesson plans/exemplars in accordance with the check list adapted by the researcher from the evaluation tool provided by the Division of Calamba City under the consent and supervision of the worthy supervisor. Their professional judgments demonstrated that the lessons were appropriate for teaching Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics. To ensure the validity and acceptability of the lesson plans, the pretest, and the posttest, the EPS and selected Master Teachers in Social Studies in the Division of Calamba were also engaged for further guidance and expertise. Moreover, a comprehensive process involving expert assessment and feedback from the Thesis Adviser, Research Director, Dean of the Graduate School, EPS of Social Studies, and one Master Teacher II were conducted to validate the instrument and the 50 items for the pretest and posttest. This was verified through the **CVR/CVI**, which achieved a score of **1.00**, signifying impeccable content validity established through unanimous expert agreement. This result reflected the instrument's excellent design, relevance, and alignment with its intended purpose. Unanimity underscored that the items were highly relevant and appropriately chosen.

Additionally, Cronbach's Alpha was employed to assess the reliability of the study. The researcher utilized the results of Cronbach's Alpha coefficients, which were **0.872** for the pretest and posttest, and **0.921** for the instrument. The following are the statistical treatments applied in the study: The Mean and Standard Deviation were used, and the 4-point Likert scale were applied to determine the level of validity and acceptability of the HEART: the Developed Lesson Exemplars in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Innovation and Culturally Responsive Education; and the frequency and percentage were employed to describe the performance of the Grade 11 Learners in the pre-test and post-test. The paired t-test for dependent samples was used to distinguish the significant difference on the performance of respondents' pretest and posttest in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics subject.

RESULTS

Table 1.1

Final List of Learning Objectives and Topics in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (p. 35-37)

MELC	Learning Objectives	Topics
Traces Kinship Ties and Social Network UCSP 11/12HSO II 1-20	<p>Define the concept of Society and its key elements</p> <p>Identify and explain the various forms of social organization (e.g., family, government, economy, education religion</p> <p>Appreciate the significance of interconnectedness in maintaining order and stability within a society.</p>	<p>How Society is Organized</p> <p>Key Concepts:</p> <p>A. Society and Social Organization</p> <p>B. Institutions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Family 2. Government, 3. Economy 4. Education 5. Religion/church
Describe the organized nature of social life and rules governing behavior UCSP11/12HSO II-21	<p>Define the Social Group</p> <p>Discuss the characteristics of social groups</p> <p>Appreciate the contributions of different groups to the development and well-being of the individual and society</p>	<p>Concept of Social Group and Social Organizations</p> <p>Key concepts:</p> <p>A. Classification of different groups according to categories</p>
Compare different social forms of social organizations according to their manifest latent functions UCSP11/12 HSO IIj- 22	<p>Describe the concept of kinship in politics and its impact on political structures, specifically political dynasties and alliances</p> <p>Discuss the role of kinship in forming political alliances and coalitions across different cultures</p> <p>Justify the effects of political dynasties on democracy and governance, with the reference to the Filipino context</p>	<p>Politics of Kinship (political Dynasty, alliances</p>

<p>Analyze social and Political Structure UCSP11/12HSO-IIj-23</p>	<p>Identify the different types of political leadership structures and how they operate across cultures.</p>	<p>Political Leadership Structures Key contents:</p>
	<p>Analyze how cultural norms and traditions influence political organizations</p>	<p>A. Political Organizations 1. Bands 2. Tribes 3. Chiefdoms states</p>
	<p>Reflect on the impact of political leadership structures on their community and society through the lens of culturally responsive education</p>	
	<p>Describe the different forms of State and non-state institutions</p>	
<p>Differentiate Functions of State and Non-State Institutions UCSP 11/12 HSO IIe-25</p>	<p>Differentiate the functions of state and non-state institutions</p>	<p>State and Non-state Institutions</p>
	<p>Appraise the state and non-state institutions in relation to personal development</p>	
<p>Evaluate how functions of education affect the lives of people in society UCSP 11/12 HSO IIf-26</p>	<p>Define the meaning of education and its functions in society</p>	
	<p>Explain the types of system of education in the Philippine context</p>	<p>Functions and the importance of Education</p>
	<p>Value the functions and significance of education in providing productive citizens based on the existing provisions</p>	<p>A. Formal Education B. Non-Formal Education</p>
<p>Analyze how religion influences culture, society, and politics UCSP 11/12 HSO IIg-27</p>	<p>Define religion and beliefs systems</p>	<p>Religious and Beliefs System</p>
	<p>Differentiate between various world religions and indigenous beliefs system</p>	<p>A. Animism B. Monotheism C. Polytheism D. Institutionalized religions E. Christianity F. Islam G. Hinduism</p>
<p>Conduct participant observation (e.g.</p>	<p>Explain the role of religion in shaping societal values and norms</p>	

Attend describe, and reflect on a religious ritual of a different group; observe elections practices UCSP11/12HSP 11g-28	Appreciate the diversity of belief system in a culturally responsive manner.	H. Buddhism
Examine Stratification from the functionalist and conflict perspectives UCSP 11/12 HSO IIg-30	Define social stratification and its key concepts Identify and explain the different forms of social stratification Reflect on ways to address social inequality	Social and political Stratification Forms of stratification Social stratification in the Philippines

Table 2.1

Level of Content Validity of the Developed Lesson Exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM Students in terms of Intellectual Property Rights Compliance

Indicators in terms of Intellectual Property Rights Compliance	\bar{X}	VI
1. The learning resource is free from plagiarism	4.00	HVR
2. The learning resource is free from copyright infringement.	4.00	HVR
3. The copyrighted materials used in the lesson exemplars are accurately cited.	3.73	HVR
4. The citation of the copyrighted material follows the prescribed format.	3.87	HVR
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.90	HVR
<i>Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Valid and Reliable (HVR) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Valid and Reliable (SVR)</i>		
<i>2.50 – 3.24 Valid and Reliable (VR) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Valid and Reliable (NVR)</i>		

Table 2.2

Level of Content Validity and Reliability of the Developed Lesson Exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM Students in terms of Learning Competencies

Indicators in terms of Learning Competencies	\bar{X}	VI
1. The content is consistent with the targeted DepEd Learning Competencies Intended for the learning area and grade level.	4.00	HVR
2. The learning objectives reflect the core content and skills	4.00	HVR
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	4.00	HVR

*Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Valid and Reliable (HVR) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Valid and Reliable (SVR)
2.50 – 3.24 Valid and Reliable (VR) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Valid and Reliable (NVR)*

Table 2.3

Level of Content Validity and Reliability of the Developed Lesson Exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM Students in terms of Instructional Design and Organization

Indicators in terms of Instructional Design and Organization	\bar{X}	VI
1. The material is appropriate for the developmental stage, needs, and experiences of learners.	4.00	HVR
2. The content enhances, supports, and contributes to achieving mastery of the intended learning competencies for the subject and grade level.	4.00	HVR
3. The material is cohesively organized and developed throughout its entirety.	4.00	HVR
4. Lesson plans demonstrate sufficient complexity and depth.	4.00	HVR
5. The content in the exemplars is inclusive and shows respect for diverse cultures.	3.87	HVR
6. The resource includes introductions, reviews, summaries, and other elements that ensure a smooth transition between lessons.	3.87	HVR
7. The material addresses various learning preferences and abilities.	4.00	HVR
8. The resource fosters advanced skills like critical thinking, creativity, experiential learning, and problem-solving, alongside 21st-century competencies.	4.00	HVR
9. Teaching methods employed are culturally appropriate and inclusive.	3.87	HVR

10. The material promotes the development of desirable values and traits.	4.00	HVR
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.96	HVR

*Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Valid and Reliable (HVR) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Valid and Reliable (SVR)
2.50 – 3.24 Valid and Reliable (VR) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Valid and Reliable (NVR)*

Table 2.4

Level of Content Validity and Reliability of the Developed Lesson Exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM Students in terms of Instructional Quality

Indicators in terms of Instructional Quality	\bar{X}	VI
1. The resource aligns with the specific objectives of the subject and grade level for which it is designed.	4.00	HVR
2. The level of difficulty is suitable for the intended audience.	4.00	HVR
3. The resource captures the interest and engagement of its target learners.	4.00	HVR
4. The content is free from any form of cultural insensitivity or social content violations.	3.87	HVR
5. The information provided is accurate and up to date.	4.00	HVR
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.97	HVR

*Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Valid and Reliable (HVR) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Valid and Reliable (SVR)
2.50 – 3.24 Valid and Reliable (VR) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Valid and Reliable (NVR)*

Table 2.5

Level of Content Validity and Reliability of the Developed Lesson Exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM Students in terms of Instructional/ Classroom Implementation

Indicators in terms of Instructional/ Classroom Implementation	\bar{X}	VI
1. Instructions are straightforward and easy to follow.	4.00	HVR
2. The time allocated for each activity is reasonable and appropriate.	3.73	HVR
3. Strategies for managing the classroom are included in the lesson exemplars.	4.00	HVR

4. Ideas flow logically and coherently throughout the material.	4.00	HVR
5. The lessons are flexible and can be adapted to accommodate diverse learners and situations.	4.00	HVR
6. The resource uses various teaching and learning approaches that cater to different individual learning needs.	4.00	HVR
7. Safety and health considerations are addressed through adequate warnings and cautionary notes where necessary.	3.87	HVR
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.94	HVR

*Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Valid and Reliable (HVR) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Valid and Reliable (SVR)
2.50 – 3.24 Valid and Reliable (VR) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Valid and Reliable (NVR)*

Table 2.6

Level of Content Validity and Reliability of the Developed Lesson Exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM Students in terms of Assessment

Indicators in terms of Instructional/ Classroom Assessment	\bar{X}	VI
1. The lesson exemplars provide useful measures and information that help the teacher evaluates learner's progress in mastering the target competencies.	4.00	HVR
2. Assessments are suitable, aligned with the objectives and content.	4.00	HVR
3. The lesson exemplar provides "self-checks," ready-made achievement tests, and/or periodic review activities.	3.73	HVR
4. The learning resource provides a variety of assessment types	4.00	HVR
5. Activities, exercises, and tasks provide for varying learning arrangements such as individual, dyad, triad, and others.	4.00	HVR
6. Assessments have clear demonstration/examples, instructions, and/or rubrics to serve as guide on how these will be used.	3.73	HVR
7. Explains the rationale behind the activities, exercises, and tasks.	4.00	HVR
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.92	HVR

*Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Valid and Reliable (HVR) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Valid and Reliable (SVR)
2.50 – 3.24 Valid and Reliable (VR) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Valid and Reliable (NVR)*

Table 3.1*Performance of 44 Grade 11 Students in the 50- item Pretest*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	0	0%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	0	0%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	0	0%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	5	11.36%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	39	88.64%
Total		44	100%
Standard Deviation		4.298	
Overall Performance		68.75	

Table 3.2*Performance of 44 Grade 11 Students in the 50- item Posttest*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	27	61.36%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	14	31.82%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	3	6.82%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0%
Total		44	100%
Standard Deviation		3.057	
Overall Performance		89.84	

Table 3.3*Test of Significant Difference between the Academic Performance in Pretest and Posttest*

Test	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		
Pretest and Posttest	-21.0909	5.15264	-27.151	.000	Significant	Reject H _o

DISCUSSION

Research Objective 1: Develop lesson exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM students.

The developed lesson exemplars in Grade 11 Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for the second quarter discussed the basic concepts and topics in UCSP following the learning competencies. In addition, the lesson exemplars had information and varied activities that cater to learners' differences, different backgrounds, experiences, and situations.

The **HEART** framework provided structures, a learner-centered approach designed to cater to diverse learning needs while fostering critical thinking and inclusivity. The acronym **HEART** stood for **Hooking**, which meant capturing students' interest at the beginning of the lesson through compelling activities, such as provoked questions, multimedia presentations, or real-life scenarios related to cultural, social, or political contexts. **Engagement** was the involvement of the students in the learning process through collaboration and participation in different activities. **Assimilation** involved learning new skills and gaining a deeper understanding by connecting new information to prior knowledge and experiences. **Responsive** meant adapting lessons to the cultural backgrounds, values, and interests of learners. This ensured inclusivity and relevance, promoted equity, and respected diversity. **Transformative** assessment encouraged students to apply learned concepts in real-world scenarios.

As highlighted by Khan et al., (2024), lesson planning was a critical process central to effective teaching and learning (Strong, 2021). It functioned as a detailed roadmap, enabling educators to design structured and engaging instructional experiences for students.

Research Objective 2: Establish the content validity and reliability of the designed lesson exemplars.

To guarantee that instructional materials were both valid and reliable, it was essential to create excellent lesson models. As instructional guides, lesson exemplars provided an organized method of presenting key concepts by coordinating teaching objectives with learning outcomes. These models had to not only satisfy curriculum requirements but also utilize creative and culturally sensitive teaching strategies to accommodate the varied learning needs of students within the framework of the Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP) course.

DepEd mandated and emphasized the central role of teachers in establishing learning environments that were responsive to learners' diversity (PPST Domain 3). This Domain underscored the importance of teachers' knowledge and understanding, as well as respect for learners' different characteristics, perspectives, and experiences as inputs to the planning and designing of lesson exemplars. Instructional materials should integrate innovative strategies and culturally responsive approaches in teaching and learning.

Content validity and reliability were anchored on the prescribed evaluation tool for the content of lesson exemplars, prescribed by the Division of Calamba based on the requirement indicated under structured criteria, including I. Intellectual Property Rights Compliance, II. Learning Competencies, III. Instructional Design and Organization of Lesson Exemplar, IV. Instructional Quality, V. Instructional/ Classroom Implementation, and VI. Assessment. These structured criteria were carefully reviewed by the subject experts and curriculum specialists and reflected in the CVR/CVI; the overall agreement among experts on the validity and reliability of all items to the designed lesson exemplar being measured was **highly valid and reliable**, with a **CVR/CVI of 1.00**.

The level of content validity of the developed lesson exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for Grade 11 STEM students in terms of Intellectual Property Rights Compliance had the general assessment was **3.90**, which was verbally interpreted as **Highly Valid and Reliable**. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Highly Valid and Reliable**. Furthermore, the indicators “The learning resource is free from plagiarism” and “The learning resource is free from copyright infringement” had the highest computed mean of **4.00**, while the indicator “The copyrighted materials used in the lesson exemplars are accurately cited” had the lowest computed mean of **3.73**.

It implies that the developed lesson exemplars in Understanding Culture, Society and Politics for Innovation and Culturally Responsive Education in terms of property rights have High Validity. The results show that Intellectual Property and Rights compliance ensures ethical integrity and credibility in instructional materials. The scores in plagiarism and copyright infringement indicators reflect adherence to best practices in academic honesty.

This finding aligned with Griffin's (2023) emphasis on the importance of proper intellectual property management in the development of culturally responsive instructional materials. According to Gay (2020), ensuring compliance with copyright laws was not only a legal requirement but also an ethical practice that underscored the credibility of educational resources.

The perfect score of **4.00** across all indicators confirmed the lesson exemplars' alignment with DepEd competencies, ensuring relevance and appropriateness for the target learners. By adhering to the required standards, the materials support the development of critical thinking and cultural awareness.

It implies that the Developed Lesson Exemplars in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics in terms of objectives have high validity. The results show that the objectives are relevant to the topic and aligned with the most essential learning competencies. Learning objectives are clear, specific, actionable, and measurable, allowing both teachers and students to track progress and outcomes more effectively.

Irvine (2020) highlighted that culturally responsive education required strict alignment with established competencies to provide equitable learning opportunities for diverse students. Additionally, Abacioglu, Volman, and Fischer (2020) emphasized that well-structured materials reflecting core competencies enhanced teachers' ability to

address multicultural classroom needs.

In terms of Instructional Design and Organization, the overall assessment yielded a score of **3.96**, classified as highly valid and reliable. Seven indicators received perfect scores of **4.00**, including those addressing logical content development and its alignment with targeted learning competencies. Statements such as "Lesson exemplars content is inclusive and respectful of diverse culture" and "The learning resource contains useful introductions, reviews, summaries, and other devices that facilitate smooth progression from one lesson to another" received a mean score of **3.87**. These indicators were likewise interpreted as highly valid and reliable, reflecting the strong alignment of the exemplars with instructional design standards and cultural inclusivity.

Table 2.3 confirms the lesson exemplars' strong alignment with the principles of effective instructional design. Indicators such as logical development and reinforcement of competencies highlight the exemplars' ability to guide learners through progressively complex concepts. The inclusion of content that respects diverse cultures and supports varied learning styles aligns with Kurian's (2023) framework for building multicultural classrooms.

Hammond (2021) highlighted that to guarantee representation, genuinely inclusive policies frequently require closer cooperation with a variety of stakeholders. This suggested that to jointly produce instructional materials and approaches, educators and curriculum developers had to actively interact with people from diverse cultural, social, and language backgrounds. To represent a range of viewpoints and guarantee equity in educational methods, it emphasized the necessity of developing partnerships with families, community leaders, and other stakeholders. This enhanced students' sense of community and improved learning outcomes.

Instructional Quality had a general assessment of **3.97**, which is verbally interpreted as highly valid and reliable. Among all five indicators, only "the learning resource" showed a slight dip to **3.87**, which was verbally interpreted as highly valid and reliable. The rest of the other indicators had a general assessment of **4.00**, which was verbally interpreted as highly valid and reliable.

The lesson exemplars exhibit excellent instructional quality, contributing effectively to achieving specific learning objectives. High scores for instructional quality reflect that the exemplars effectively meet learning objectives, ensuring content relevance and accuracy. The indicators demonstrate alignment with DepEd's requirements, with strengths in engaging students and ensuring content accuracy. The slightly lower score for being "free from social content violations" suggests potential areas for enhancing review to address any unintended biases. The results underlined the critical role of accurate, engaging, and culturally sensitive materials in enhancing student motivation and learning.

The findings aligned with Irvine's (2020) assertion that high-quality instructional materials not only met learning goals but also inspired student engagement. Accuracy and relevance, as noted by Hammond (2021), were critical for fostering trust and

credibility in culturally responsive education.

Instructional/Classroom implementation was rated as Highly Valid and Reliable (**3.94**). The scores indicated strong classroom adaptability and clear instructional design, which were crucial for effective classroom implementation. The slightly lower score (**3.73**) for time allocation suggested that some activities needed adjustment to better align with classroom schedules or optimize lesson pacing. Similarly, the indicator for safety noted (**3.87**), which highlighted the need to integrate more specific safety guidance.

This means that effective instructional implementation of Culturally Responsive Education in the classroom carries significant positive implications for teaching, learning, and overall student development. Lessons and activities that are designed to acknowledge learners to be respected and heard, learning becomes more meaningful, engaging, and relevant to students lived experiences. Lessons that are flexible and straightforward accommodate diverse learners and different situations. The results also imply that learning needs are addressed and enhance student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. Students and teachers benefited from clear and adaptable lesson plans that support effective classroom management and responsiveness to diverse needs.

This aligned with the emphasis of Ladson-Billings (1995) on the importance of adaptability and clarity in culturally responsive teaching, where teachers needed to adapt instructional strategies to fit the cultural contexts of their students while ensuring that learning goals and expectations were clear and accessible to all.

Classroom Assessment had a general assessment of **3.92**, which was verbally interpreted as HVR. Five out of seven (5/7) indicators were rated **4.00**, considered exemplary and perfect, which reflected an impressive result for the classroom assessment. On the other hand, the criterion "Assessments have clear demonstrations/examples, instructions, and/or rubrics to serve as a guide on how these will be used" and "The lesson exemplar provides 'self-checks,' ready-made achievement tests, and/or periodic review activities" received a lower score of **3.73** but were still verbally interpreted as High Valid and Reliable.

The high scores for alignment and variety indicate that the assessments effectively support learning objectives and a comprehensive evaluation of student progress. The slightly lower scores for self-checks and rubric clarity (**3.73**) suggest a need to provide more detailed explanations and examples to enhance teacher and student understanding.

These findings conformed with Kotluk and Aydin's (2021) advocacy for diverse and clearly defined assessment strategies, which were essential for supporting critical thinking and ensuring equitable evaluation of students' performance.

The evaluation process confirmed that the lesson exemplars met the dual objectives of fostering innovation and promoting cultural responsiveness. Through teacher feedback and expert validation, the exemplars demonstrated their ability to engage learners from diverse backgrounds, enhance cultural competence, and integrate

inclusive teaching strategies.

Research Objective 3: Identify if there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the Grade 11 STEM students.

Pretests and posttests were designed to assess how much students had learned about a particular topic. According to Paul Richard Kuehn (2021) in his blog, these tests spanned all subjects that students engaged with during a quarter or semester. It wasn't essential for students to know the answers to every question on the pretest, but it was expected that they would use any prior knowledge to provide reasonable answers. With the improvement in their understanding, students were expected to answer more questions correctly on the posttest, which was administered after one month of implementation. The students' posttest performance improved after using the lesson exemplars designed with culturally responsive education, grounded in the HEART framework.

This objective aimed to measure the impact of the lesson exemplars on student performance. A significant improvement in posttest scores confirmed the materials' effectiveness in addressing gaps in knowledge and fostering understanding of culturally diverse perspectives. This finding supported the adoption of these exemplars in broader educational contexts to address academic challenges and knowledge gaps, particularly in diverse classrooms.

Table 3.1 showed that most students, or **88.64%**, scored below the passing mark in the pretest before the implementation of developed lesson exemplars, which highlighted significant gaps in prior knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. Only **11.36%** of students achieved a "Fairly Satisfactory" grade. No one got satisfactory or above, 0% satisfactory, very satisfactory, or outstanding. **4.298** moderate high Standard Deviation result indicated that the scores were spread out over a wide range, and there was greater variability in the performance during the pretest. Most of the students struggled, and the test was difficult.

These results reflect the need for target instructional materials that address foundational knowledge gaps. Low pretest scores highlight the importance of the instructional design's role in improving student outcomes. They serve as a baseline for measuring the effectiveness of the teaching methods and materials introduced later.

Muniz (2020) emphasized the importance of culturally responsive pre-assessments in understanding diverse learners' starting points. These findings underscored the importance of diagnostic assessments to identify and address learners' starting points, particularly in diverse educational settings.

The posttest results demonstrated remarkable improvement, with **61.36%** of students achieving an "Outstanding" performance, 31.82% receiving a very satisfactory rating, and **6.82%** earning a satisfactory rating. No student "Did Not Meet Expectations." The substantial improvement in posttest scores demonstrated the success of the exemplars in enhancing student understanding and engagement. At the same time, it had

a lower standard deviation (SD) of **3.057**, indicating more consistent performance among students, as the data points were closely clustered around the mean. This indicated little differentiation between high and low performers, and the spread of scores was close.

The Developed and Validated Lesson Exemplars in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics for innovation and Culturally Responsive Education have significant implications for enhancing students' academic performance and overall learning experience. These implications are grounded in the innovative and culturally responsive approach used to design the lesson exemplars. The study's implications underscore the transformative potential of using validated lesson exemplars to promote higher engagement, better understanding, and improved performance.

This corresponded with Yimwilai's (2020) findings that innovative and culturally responsive teaching strategies dramatically improved student engagement and achievement and foster a more inclusive learning environment.

The test of significance between the performance of the group in the pre-test and post-test showed that the probability value was **.000**, which is less than the level of significance at **.05**. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the students on the pre-test and post-test.

The significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores indicates that students' learning outcomes have improved after the intervention and the use of the developed lesson exemplars. The p-value of **.000** (which is less than the set significance level of **0.05**) confirms that this improvement is unlikely to have occurred by chance. By rejecting the null hypothesis, it is concluded that there is a meaningful impact caused by the developed lesson exemplars that are innovative and culturally responsive in the teaching method. These materials not only enhance academic performance but also foster cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness, aligning with contemporary educational goals for diversity and equity.

These results affirmed the success of the instructional materials in improving student performance. The findings resonated with Howard and Guillaume's (2020) assertion that culturally responsive pedagogy promoted deeper understanding and better learning outcomes and improved academic success, and holistic development.

Conclusions

The study sought to develop, validate, and evaluate lesson exemplars for Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP), focused on fostering innovation and cultural responsiveness in education. The findings from the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data revealed the following key insights:

1. Development of Lesson Exemplars

The lesson exemplars were meticulously designed using the ADDIE model to align with the DepEd competencies and the principles of culturally responsive education (CRE).

The process emphasized inclusivity, relevance, and engagement to address the diverse cultural backgrounds and learning needs of Grade 11 STEM students.

2. Content Validity and Reliability

The developed exemplars were found as highly valid and reliable across all dimensions, including intellectual property compliance, alignment with learning competencies, instructional design, instructional quality, classroom implementation, and assessment. This high level of validity ensured the exemplars met both educational standards and the needs of a diverse learner population.

3. Educational Impact of Lesson Exemplars

A significant improvement in the post-test scores of students compared to their pre-test performance confirmed the effectiveness of the lesson exemplars in addressing knowledge gaps and fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The remarkable shift in academic performance from most students not meeting expectations in the pre-test to most achieving "Outstanding" in the post-test demonstrated the transformative potential of culturally responsive and innovative instructional materials.

4. Cultural Responsiveness and Inclusivity

The results highlighted the exemplars' success in integrating cultural contexts into teaching practices, fostering empathy, respect, and understanding among students. This alignment with CRE principles promoted an inclusive learning environment where students feel represented and valued.

5. Assessment Strategies

The lesson exemplars incorporated varied and well-aligned assessment methods, supporting critical thinking, creativity, and meaningful evaluation of student learning. While some minor refinements in self-checks and rubrics were recommended, the overall assessment framework effectively supported learning goals.

6. Teacher and Stakeholder Feedback

Validation by subject matter experts and educators confirmed the practicality, adaptability, and relevance of the lesson exemplars for classroom use. Their feedback further underscored the exemplars' potential as a resource for enhancing culturally responsive pedagogy.

In conclusion, the study successfully developed and validated lesson exemplars that were innovative, inclusive, and culturally responsive, addressing both academic and cultural gaps in UCSP instruction. These materials were not only aligned with educational standards but also effective in enhancing students' academic outcomes, cultural competence, and critical thinking skills. The findings highlighted the value of integrating cultural responsiveness into instructional design, reinforcing the importance of inclusive education in fostering equitable learning opportunities.

This study contributed to the body of knowledge on culturally responsive education and provided a model for future initiatives aimed at enhancing curriculum and instruction in diverse educational settings. By fostering empathy, respect, and critical awareness among students the validated lesson exemplars hold the potential to prepare learners to thrive in an interconnected and multicultural world.

Recommendations

Building upon the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were proposed to enhance the impact of the developed lesson exemplars and further promote innovative and culturally responsive education:

1. For Educators: Implement Culturally Responsive Practices

1.1 Integrate Lesson Exemplars into Regular Instruction: Teachers are encouraged to adopt the validated lesson exemplars in their UCSP classes, ensuring alignment with the DepEd curriculum while fostering cultural awareness and inclusivity.

1.2 Provide Continuous Feedback: Teachers should document and share their experiences using the lesson exemplars, identifying areas for improvement and adaptation to meet the evolving needs of students.

1.3 Professional Development: Educators should participate in training and workshops on culturally responsive pedagogy to effectively implement the exemplars and address the diverse needs of learners.

2. For School Administrators: Institutionalize Culturally Responsive Education

2.1 Support Teachers: Allocate resources, such as time for collaborative planning and access to materials, to facilitate the seamless integration of the exemplars into the curriculum.

2.2 Monitor and Evaluate Implementation: Develop a feedback mechanism to assess the impact of the lesson exemplars on student outcomes and teacher effectiveness, enabling data-driven decisions for refinement.

2.3 Promote an Inclusive School Culture: Encourage practices that celebrate cultural diversity, such as multicultural events, projects, and classroom activities that build on the exemplars' themes.

3. For Curriculum Developers: Expand the Scope of Lesson Exemplars

3.1 Develop Exemplars for Other Grade Levels and Subjects: Use the model established in this study to create culturally responsive materials for other courses, ensuring a wider impact across the curriculum.

3.2 Incorporate Emerging Issues: To make the exemplars more relevant to contemporary educational goals, include topics related to global citizenship,

sustainability, and digital literacy.

3.3 Standardize Cultural Representation: Develop guidelines to ensure balanced and accurate cultural representation in all instructional materials.

4. For Policymakers: Advocate for Culturally Responsive Education

4.1 Policy Support for Inclusion: Create policies that mandate the integration of culturally responsive practices into teacher training and curriculum design.

4.2 Incentivize Innovation: Provide funding and recognition for schools and educators who demonstrate excellence in implementing innovative, culturally inclusive teaching strategies.

4.3 Support Research and Development: Encourage partnerships between schools, universities, and organizations to conduct research on the long-term effects of culturally responsive education on student success.

5. For Future Researchers: Further Exploration of Culturally Responsive Pedagogy

5.1 Expand the Study Scope: Conduct similar studies across different regions, educational levels, and cultural contexts to validate the replicability of the lesson exemplars.

5.2 Evaluate Long-Term Impact: Investigate how culturally responsive teaching strategies affect students' academic performance, social skills, and global competencies over time.

5.3 Explore Student Perspectives: Include student feedback to assess how culturally responsive education influences their attitudes, engagement, and cultural understanding.

Adopting these recommendations will strengthen the integration of innovative and culturally responsive education into the Philippine educational system. By building on the successes of this study, educators and stakeholders can collectively ensure that students are equipped with the skills, knowledge, and empathy needed to thrive in a diverse and interconnected world.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, and its Implementing Rules and Regulations, the researcher upheld the right to privacy as specified in the Laguna College of Business and Arts Research Manual. The study prioritized protecting respondents' privacy and security since it relied on volunteer respondents. To avoid any ethical concerns during the research process, these considerations were addressed beforehand. The key areas focused on were confidentiality (keeping information secret), privacy (protecting personal information), anonymity (not identifying respondents), and acknowledging the works of others used in the study.

The study upheld ethical standards by providing clear informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, maintaining confidentiality, and fostering a respectful environment. The researcher avoided discriminatory language, guaranteed data privacy, and acknowledged the contributions of prior scholarly work.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her deepest gratitude to the following people who gave their time and effort to impart knowledge and give assistance for the better outcomes of her manuscript:

Dr. Melchor A. Villapando, her thesis adviser and statistician, for providing invaluable guidance, patience, encouragement, and support throughout this research journey amidst his numerous responsibilities.

Dr. Ma. Lorena M, Tagala, for being her research thesis writing professor, for her tireless efforts in guiding the author through the intricacies of academic writing. Her meticulous attention to detail and constructive feedback have greatly enriched the quality of this thesis;

Grade 11 Kamagong section, Batch 2024-2025, and their adviser, Ma'am Hazel Ann Llamas, for their active participation during the execution of her study and in the conduct of different phases of her thesis. Your cooperation and engagement made this research possible and meaningful;

Principal, Dr. Danilo S. Tungol, for granting approval to conduct her study at the school. His trust and support have provided the foundation for this project's success;

EPS, Ma'am Marivic Calderon, Ma'am Eloisa Valiente, Sir Dennis Batolena, and Ma'am Criselda De Chavez for sharing their expertise and invaluable insights, which enriched the depth and credibility of her research. Their willingness to share their time and knowledge is truly commendable;

Araling Panlipunan Teachers in the Division of Calamba City and private institution for proficiently validating the developed lesson exemplars in Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics. Their constructive critiques, thoughtful recommendations, and unwavering support have greatly contributed to the refinement and improvement of this study;

Panelists, Dr. Enrico Jocson, the Chairman, Dean Alfred G. Perez, and Dr. Ma. Lorena M. Tagala, for their invaluable time, expertise, and insightful feedback and dedication to academic excellence and commitment to fostering scholarly inquiry inspire the author to continue striving for growth and innovation;

John Vincent Tiong, her former student, for generously sharing his artistic talent by creating the illustration featured on the cover page of the lesson exemplars;

Krishna Camille B. Ferrer, her beloved daughter, for being the reliable partner in this endeavour, for her thoughtful insights, and for the many times she extended her hand to help with the technical aspects, editing, and organizing of this work despite her busy schedules;

Kaiden "ang unang" Apo, for being a constant source of joy, her oasis of rest, offering your lola a moment of peace and happiness, his laughter, innocence, and boundless energy brought light to her days and reminded her of the beauty of life amidst the challenges she faced;

Inay, for being her inspiration and her greatest blessing. Her prayers and

unwavering faith in her dreams have been the author's greatest source of strength;

Her sissy classmates Almira, Micah, Joan, Selene, RM, Donyabels, Beth, Marlene and Cora, their support, understanding, and endless belief in her abilities have guided her through every challenge and triumph in this journey;

Ramil, her dearest husband, for being consistently motivating and a source of positivity throughout this journey. His encouraging words and faith in her abilities have meant the world to the author. This research would not have been possible without his love and selflessness. He has been the pillar of support, cheerleader, and author's reminder that every challenge is an opportunity for growth. Thank you for paying her tuition fees as well;

Ferrer Family, whose unconditional love, support, and understanding have been her anchor during this endeavor. Their sacrifices and encouragement have always motivated the author to do her best. Their presence has been a blessing, and this work is dedicated to you as a testament to the joy and strength you bring into her life. This achievement reflects the sacrifices, patience, and boundless love have have all given her; and

Last, God Almighty, for His unwavering guidance and wisdom throughout this journey. His presence provided her with the strength and courage to persevere, especially during challenging times. "Papuri at Pasasalamat!"

REFERENCES

- Abacioglu et al., (2020). Teachers' multicultural attitudes and perspectives taking abilities as factors in culturally responsive teaching. *The British journal of educational psychology*, 90(3), 736–752. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12328>
- Department of Education. (2023). MATATAG: Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa agenda. Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/matatag-agenda/>
- Department of Education. (2017). Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Department of Education. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/DO_s2017_042.pdf
- Fischer, A., et al., (2020). Framing a curriculum for the twenty-first century competencies. In D. Sale (Ed.), *Creative Teachers: Cognitive Science and Technology* (pp. 243–262). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-3469-0_7
- Gay, G. (2020). *Culturally Responsive Teaching: Theory, Research, and Practice*. Third Edition. Multicultural Education Series. Teachers College Press.
- Griffin, D. (2023). A Framework for Culturally Responsive Lesson Design. *Education Doctorate Dissertations*. 16. <https://openriver.winona.edu/educationeddissertations/16>
- Hammond, Z. (2021). Liberatory Education: Integrating the Science of Learning and Culturally Responsive Practice. *American Educator*, 45(2), 4.
- Howard, T.C. & Guillaume, A.M. (2020). *Innovative Approaches to Culturally Responsive Education: Lessons from the Field*.
- Irvine, J. J. (2020). *Culturally responsive teaching and educational equity: Extending the movement*. Teachers College Press
- Khan, S. et al., (2024). Effect of Lesson Planning on Academic Performance: Evidence from the Elementary Level Classroom. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, 8(1), 169–177. [https://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2024\(8-1\)15](https://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2024(8-1)15)
- Kotluk, N., & Aydin, H. (2021). Culturally relevant/sustaining pedagogy in a diverse

- urban classroom: Challenges of pedagogy for Syrian refugee youths and teachers in Turkey. *British Educational Research Journal*, 47(4), 900–921.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/BERJ.3700>
- Kurian, N. (2023). Building inclusive, multicultural early years classrooms: Strategies for a culturally responsive ethic of care. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 52(5), 863–878.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-023-01456-0>
- Ladson-Billings, G. (1995). Toward a theory of culturally relevant pedagogy. *American Educational Research Journal*, 32(3), 465–491.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312032003465>
- Muñiz, J. (2020, September 23). Culturally responsive teaching: A reflection guide. *New America*. <https://www.newamerica.org/education-policy/policy-papers/culturally-responsive-teaching-competencies/>
- Kuehn, P. R. (2021). Function and importance of pre- and post-tests [Blog post]. *The Arena Media Brands*. Retrieved from
<https://owcation.com/academia/PrePost-Test-A-Diagnostic-Tool-For-More-Effective-Teaching-of-EFL-Students>
discover.hubpages.com+11researchgate.net+11research.brighton.ac.uk+11
- Republic of the Philippines. (2013). Republic Act No. 10533: Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. *Official Gazette*. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republic-act-no-10533/>
- Smith, T., Avraamidou, L., & Adams, J. D. (2022). Culturally relevant/responsive and sustaining pedagogies in science education: Theoretical perspectives and curriculum implications. *Cultural Studies of Science Education*, 17(3), 637–660. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11422-021-10082-4>
- Strong, M. (2021). *The art of lesson planning: Strategies for effective teaching*. Routledge. “Lesson planning is a fundamental process that lies at the heart of effective teaching and learning” (Strong, 2021, as cited in Khan, Siraj, & Ilyas, 2024, p. 170).
- Yimwilai, S. (2020). The Effects of Project-based Learning in an EFL Classroom. *Journal of Liberal Arts, Maejo University*, 8(2), 214–232.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00098650903505415>
-